

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TBLT IN IMPROVING LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY COMPARED TO TRADITIONAL METHODS

Ug'iloY Xakimova

English teacher of department of Languages,

“Yangi Asr” university

E-mail: ogiloy0710@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14575094>

Abstract. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) has emerged as an innovative approach in language education, emphasizing the use of meaningful tasks to promote language acquisition. This article reviews the effectiveness of TBLT compared to traditional methods, increasingly cited by scholars as superior in developing overall language proficiency. By examining various studies and expert opinions, this paper seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how TBLT benefits language learners.

Key words: TBLT, input, output, real-life communication, form-focused, meaning focused, pre-task, while-task, post task

Introduction

Language teaching methodologies have evolved significantly, with TBLT gaining considerable attention. Unlike traditional methods, which often rely on rote memorization and grammar-translation exercises, TBLT focuses on the practical use of language. This article seeks to examine the effectiveness of TBLT in improving language proficiency, supported by scientific scholars' opinions.

Effectiveness of TBLT in Methodology

1. Task Authenticity. According to Guvendir (2020), TBLT is a method of teaching a second language that focuses on engaging learners in real-life communication through task completion. This particular approach is centered on a task but also includes preliminary and follow-up stages before and after the main task. Each task phase has its own aim through completing the tasks students can enhance not only their speaking skills but also writing, listening, and reading skills. Guvendir and Hardacre (2020) states that on pre-task stage focusing on form gives a chance for students to think about the grammar and vocabulary they will require before beginning the task. By utilizing that method teacher can grab students' attention to target forms and while performing the main task it can be very essential to solve problems which related to forms. Students can find each phase of the task enjoyable, low-stressful and also, they can produce their input in real-world scenarios with imitating by their chosen figure.

2. Communicative Competence. By focusing on practical tasks, TBLT facilitates the development of communicative competence, enabling learners to use language effectively and appropriately in various contexts. In output phase students share their ideas and through individual or group work support their preference by adding target form to their both written and oral speech. Teachers who prompt students to pay attention to language structures during communicative activities are more successful than those who never encourage them to focus on form, or who only do so in isolated grammar lessons (Lightbown, 2014). Moreover, through performance students can utilize new vocabularies in a meaningful context. TBLT approach is appealed to today's students, according to Krashen (1985), learners acquire language in a single manner, which is by receiving understandable in a relaxed setting.

3. Learner-Centered Approach. TBLT is inherently learner-centered, catering to individual learners' needs and promoting active participation and self-directed learning.

Traditional language acquisition methods predominantly emphasize the importance of grammar rules and extensive vocabulary lists. In traditional method mostly form-focused that has its own advantages and used for a long time by ESL teachers very effectively, however now young generation can't accept this kind of outdated approach all the time in learning process. These approaches often result in passive learning, where students focus heavily on memorizing linguistic structures and words without necessarily understanding their practical use in real-life contexts. This memorization-centered approach can inadvertently contribute to a learning environment where students might excel in theoretical knowledge yet struggle with applying what they have learned in everyday situations. Prabhu (1987) identifies that traditional methods focus heavily on structure, which may hinder expressive language use. Consequently, the lack of real-world applicability inherent in traditional methods may lead to disengagement among learners, as they find the content less relevant to their personal experiences or communicative needs. This gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application highlights the limitations of traditional methods in fostering active and meaningful language learning.

Conclusion

TBLT proves to be a more effective approach in improving language proficiency compared to traditional methods. It fosters a realistic and engaging learning environment that motivates learners and enhances their ability to use language

practically. Continued research and adaptation of TBLT can lead to even more effective language teaching strategies. Studies indicate that learners often show improvement in practical language skills and confidence in using the language when taught through TBLT. Traditional methods, while effective for understanding linguistic structures, may not translate as effectively to real-world language use.

In summary, TBLT provides an innovative framework that potentially surpasses traditional teaching methods in enhancing practical language skills and learner engagement. For further exploration, empirical research comparing specific outcomes between these methodologies would be beneficial in drawing more definitive conclusions.

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